

The Fetal Medicine
Foundation

16TH World Congress In Fetal Medicine

Slovenia 2017

16TH WORLD CONGRESS IN FETAL MEDICINE

Sunday 25th June 2017

Joint session with Eurofoetus

09:10 - 11:00	Lung abnormalities
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 - 12:40	Brain abnormalities
12:40 - 13:00	The artificial placenta
13:00 - 14:30	Lunch Break
14:30 - 16:15	Open spina bifida
16:15 - 17:00	Fetal anemia
17:00 - 18:00	Coffee break
18:00 - 20:00	Fetal growth restriction

Monday 26th June 2017

Joint session with Eurofoetus

09:00 - 09:40	Placental abnormalities
09:40 - 11:00	Complications in twins
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 - 12:45	Complications in twins
12:45 - 13:00	Long term outcome in complicated MC twins
13:00 - 14:30	Lunch Break
14:30 - 15:00	Lower urinary tract obstruction
15:00 - 17:00	Screening and diagnosis of chromosomal abnormalities
17:00 - 18:00	Coffee break
18:00 - 18:10	Fetal cells in maternal blood
18:10 - 20:00	Clinical genetics and fetal medicine

Tuesday 27th June 2017

09:00 - 11:00	Prediction and prevention of preterm birth
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 - 13:00	Congenital heart defects
13:00 - 14:30	Lunch Break
14:30 - 16:20	Congenital heart defects
16:20 - 16:30	Fetal bowel dilation
16:30 - 17:30	Coffee break
17:30 - 19:00	First trimester scan

Wednesday 28th June 2017

10:00 - 11:00	Prediction of preeclampsia
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 - 13:00	Prediction of preeclampsia
13:00 - 14:30	Lunch Break
14:30 - 16:30	Prevention of preeclampsia
16:30 - 16:45	Early screening tests – effect on healthcare costs
16:45 - 17:00	Intrapartum mortality and severe asphyxia

Thursday 29th June 2017

09:00 - 11:00	Maternal fetal disease
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 - 13:00	Labor and delivery
13:00 - 14:30	Lunch Break

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Sunday 25th June 2017: Joint session with Eurofoetus

08:00 - 11:00 Registration

08:00 - 09:10
09:10 - 11:00

Welcome

Lung abnormalities

Discussants: Jan Deprest (Belgium), Greg Ryan (Canada)

CDH: natural history

CDH: stomach in contact with the bladder

CDH: prenatal prediction of outcome by LHR in the USA

CDH: prenatal prediction of pulmonary hypertension

CDH: prenatal prediction of morbidity in first 8 years of life

CDH: TOTAL trial

CDH: prenatal removal of the balloon after FETO

CDH: trans-placental sildenafil as an adjunct to FETO

CDH: Extracellular vesicles in the tracheal fluid after FETO

Bronchopulmonary sequestration: intrafetal laser

Bronchopulmonary sequestration: intrafetal laser

Use of new intrauterine shunt

Discussion

Kypros Nicolaides (UK)

Greg Ryan (Canada)

Cesar Meller (Argentina)

Anthony Johnson (USA)

Francesca Russo (Belgium)

Patrice Eastwood (Belgium)

Jan Deprest (Belgium)

Jan Deprest (Belgium)

Francesca Russo (Belgium)

Nicola Persico (Italy)

Rogelio Cruz-Martinez (Mexico)

Brigitte Strizek (Germany)

Lone Nikoline Nørgaard (Denmark)

11:00 - 11:30

Coffee break

11:30 - 12:40

Brain abnormalities

Discussant: Yves Ville (France), Elisenda Eixarch (Spain)

11:30 - 11:45

Ventriculomegaly: natural history

11:45 - 12:00

Ventriculomegaly: prenatal diagnosis and management

12:00 - 12:10

Ventriculomegaly: prenatal assessment and outcome

12:10 - 12:17

Ventriculomegaly: in utero ventriculostomy

12:17 - 12:24

Mnemonic aid in assessment of anterior complex

12:24 - 12:40

Special findings in neurosonography

12:40 - 13:00

The artificial placenta

Dominic Thompson (UK)

Elisenda Eixarch (Spain)

Eldad Katorza (Israel)

Yves Ville (France)

Angela Ranzini (USA)

Ritsuko Pooh (Japan)

Alan Flake (USA)

13:00 - 14:30

Lunch break

14:30 - 16:15

Open spina bifida

Discussants: Jan Deprest (Belgium), Dominic Thompson (UK)

14:30 - 14:45

OSB: neurosurgical goals of spina bifida repair

14:45 - 14:53

OSB: need for leak-proof repair

14:53 - 15:00

OSB: Swiss experience with open fetal surgery

15:00 - 15:07

OSB: prenatal prediction of postnatal shunting after fetal surgery

15:07 - 15:17

OSB: long term outcome after open fetal surgery

15:17 - 15:27

OSB: pennatal and motor outcome after fetoscopic surgery

15:27 - 15:37

OSB: outcome after fetoscopic surgery

15:37 - 15:44

OSB: cerebellar Doppler velocimetry in fetal rats

15:44 - 16:01

OSB: distinction from limited dorsal myeloschisis

16:01 - 16:08

OSB: Ultrasound based 3D model printing for training purposes

16:08 - 16:15

Discussion

16:15 - 17:00

Fetal anemia

Discussant: Kypros Nicolaides (UK)

16:15 - 16:20

Background to treatment

16:20 - 16:27

Postponing early fetal transfusion with IVIG

16:27 - 16:34

MRI of umbilical vein in prediction of fetal anemia

16:34 - 16:41

Timing for sequential intrauterine transfusion

16:41 - 17:00

Discussion

Dominic Thompson (UK)

Luc Joyeux (Belgium)

Martin Meuli (Switzerland)

Ladina Vonzun (Switzerland)

Alan Flake (USA)

Denise Pedreira (Brazil)

Michael Belfort (USA)

Enrique Gil Guevara (USA)

Jean-Marie Jouannic (France)

Ahmet Baschat (USA)

Kypros Nicolaides (UK)

Carolien Zwiers (Netherlands)

Ditte Jørgensen (Denmark)

Jesus Rodriguez Galvo (Spain)

17:00 - 18:00

Coffee break

18:00 - 20:00

Fetal Growth Restriction

Discussants: Gerry Visser (Netherlands), Zarko Alfrevic (UK)

18:00 - 18:10

Fetal growth charts: WHO

18:10 - 18:20

Fetal growth charts: which ones to use

18:20 - 18:35

Assessment of fetal growth by MRI

18:35 - 18:45

FGR: cause of disease in adulthood

18:45 - 18:52

FGR: relation to renal dysfunction in adulthood

18:52 - 19:00

FGR: volumetric MRI of fetal brain

19:00 - 19:07

FGR: screening by 1st trimester growth

19:07 - 19:14

Early FGR: effect of pravastatin on fetal and uterine Doppler

19:14 - 19:30

Early FGR: RCT on sildenafil therapy

19:30 - 19:45

Early FGR: management

19:45 - 20:00

Discussion

Kurt Hecher (Germany)

Gerry Visser (Netherlands)

Jacques Jani (Belgium)

Gerry Visser (Netherlands)

Jansina Genra (Brazil)

Eldad Katorza (Israel)

Mauro Parra-Cordero (Chile)

Stamatis Pietousis (Greece)

Zarko Alfrevic (UK)

Ahmet Baschat (USA)

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Monday 26th June 2017: Joint session with Eurofoetus

09:00 - 09:48	Placental abnormalities Discussants: Jan Deprest (Belgium), Michael Belfort (USA)	Jeni Panaitova (UK) Michael Belfort (USA) George Attilakos (UK)
09:00 - 09:10	Placenta accreta: screening by ultrasound at 11-13 weeks	
09:10 - 09:25	Placenta accreta: medical and surgical treatment	
09:25 - 09:40	Vasa previa	
09:40 - 12:45	Complications in twins Discussants: Yves Ville (France), Liesbeth Lewi (Belgium)	
09:40 - 09:55	Video demonstration: training for fetoscopic laser surgery	Roland Devlieger (Belgium)
09:55 - 10:10	Video demonstration: placental perfusion studies	Liesbeth Lewi (Belgium)
10:10 - 10:17	TTTS: prediction from site of placental cord insertion	Nada Mourad Tawfic (Belgium)
10:17 - 10:24	MC twins: significance of placental cord insertion	Asma Khalil (UK)
10:24 - 10:31	TAPS: quantification of discordant placental echogenicity	Christian Bamberg (Germany)
10:31 - 10:41	TAPS: management	Yves Ville (France)
10:41 - 10:48	sFGR: definition and outcome	Asma Khalil (UK)
10:48 - 10:55	sFGR: placental microRNA 190a	Tak Yeung Leung (Hong Kong)
10:55 - 11:00	Discussion	
11:00 - 11:30 Coffee break		
11:30 - 11:37	ROM after fetoscopy: predictors	Yves Ville (France)
11:37 - 11:44	ROM after fetoscopy at <26 w: predictors of outcome	Alexander Engels (Belgium)
11:44 - 11:51	DC twins: outcome after PROM in one sac at <20 w	Shlomo Lipitz (Israel)
11:51 - 11:58	Short cervix at laser therapy: cerclage	Anthony Johnson (USA)
11:58 - 12:05	Short cervix at laser therapy: pessary	Elena Carreras (Spain)
12:05 - 12:12	Selective fetocide in MC twins: radiofrequency	Greg Ryan (Canada)
12:12 - 12:19	Selective fetocide in MC twins: bipolar coagulation	Kurt Hecher (Germany)
12:19 - 12:26	Dichorionic triplets: management options	Petya Chaveeva (Bulgaria)
12:26 - 12:33	MC twins: MCA PSV in survivor after selective cord occlusion	Katrine Vasehus Schou (Denmark)
12:33 - 12:45	Discussion	
12:45 - 13:00	Long term outcome in complicated MC twins	Enrico Lopriore (Netherlands)
13:00 - 14:30 Lunch break		
14:30 - 15:00	Lower urinary tract obstruction Discussants: Jan Deprest (Belgium), Greg Ryan (Canada)	
14:30 - 14:45	Fetal surgery	Greg Ryan (Canada)
14:45 - 14:52	Fetal cystoscopy	Yves Ville (France)
14:52 - 14:59	Urethroplasty with a coronary angioplasty balloon catheter	Marzena Debska (Poland)
15:00 - 17:00	Screening and diagnosis of chromosomal abnormalities Discussants: Kypros Nicolaidis (UK), Mark Evans (USA)	
15:00 - 15:10	Introduction	Kypros Nicolaidis (UK)
15:10 - 15:20	Invasive testing for all pregnancies	Mark Evans (USA)
15:20 - 15:27	cfDNA: meta-analysis on performance of screening	Mar Gil (Spain)
15:27 - 15:34	cfDNA: test failure	
15:34 - 15:41	importance of measuring fetal fraction	Maximilian Schmid (Austria)
15:41 - 15:51	implication of failed result due to low fetal fraction	Peter Benn (USA)
15:51 - 16:00	accounting for and reducing test failures	Howard Cuckle (Israel)
16:00 - 16:07	Discussion	
16:07 - 16:14	RCT: 1st trimester combined test vs. ultrasound and cfDNA	Oliver Kagan (Germany)
16:14 - 16:21	cfDNA: screening strategies	Francesca Grati (Italy)
16:21 - 16:28	cfDNA: effect on detected major chromosomal aberrations	Pavel Calda (Czechia)
16:28 - 16:35	cfDNA: screening beyond trisomies 21, 18, 13	
16:35 - 16:42	sex chromosome aneuploidies	Francesca Grati (Italy)
16:42 - 17:00	rare autosomal trisomies	Peter Benn (USA)
17:00 - 18:00	diagnosis of spinal muscular atrophy	Min Chen (China)
17:00 - 18:00	Discussion	
17:00 - 18:00 Coffee break		
18:00 - 18:10	Fetal cells in maternal blood	Mark Evans (USA)
18:10 - 20:00	Clinical genetics and fetal medicine Discussants: Tessa Homfray (UK), Rabih Chadou (Germany)	
18:10 - 18:20	Introduction	Tessa Homfray (UK)
18:20 - 18:27	Whole genome sequencing: detection of pathogenic CNVs	Richard Choy (Hong Kong)
18:27 - 18:34	Whole exome sequencing: fetal brain defects	Liran Hershch (Israel)
18:34 - 18:41	Whole exome sequencing: fetal akinesia syndrome	Theresa Reischer (Austria)
18:41 - 18:50	Presentation of cases	Tessa Homfray (UK)
18:50 - 19:00	Guidance from an anomaly to a syndrome by GPS	Juergen Blumenthal (France)
19:00 - 19:46	Ultrasound diagnosis of genetic syndromes	Rabih Chadou (Germany)
19:46 - 20:00	Discussion	

Tuesday 27th June 2017

09:00 - 11:00	Prediction and prevention of preterm birth Discussants: Robert Romero (USA), Zarko Alfirevic (UK)	
09:00 - 09:07	Spontaneous preterm birth in IVF pregnancies: meta-analysis	Paolo Cavoretto (Italy)
09:07 - 09:14	Relation between vaginal microbiome and amniotic fluid 'sludge'	Alan Hatanaka (Brazil)
09:14 - 09:21	Need for amniocentesis prior to cerclage	Jiri Vojtech (Czechia)
09:21 - 09:28	Usefulness of antenatal corticosteroids	Gerry Visser (Netherlands)
09:28 - 09:35	Preterm labor arrest: meta-analysis on maintenance tocolysis	Alexandros Sotiriadis (Greece)
09:35 - 09:40	Discussion	
09:40 - 09:47	PPROM at <24w: expectant management	Oliver Kagan (Germany)
09:47 - 09:54	PPROM at 16-24w: PPRMEXIL-III trial on amnioinfusion	Annemijn de Ruigh (Netherlands)
09:54 - 10:01	PPROM at 34-36w: IPD meta-analysis on early delivery	Annemijn de Ruigh (Netherlands)
10:01 - 10:08	PPROM: discussion	
10:08 - 10:15	Cervix <15 mm: Cerclage vs. vaginal progesterone	Athena Souka (Greece)
10:15 - 10:25	Cervix <25 mm: PESAPRO trial of cervical pessary vs. vaginal progesterone	Sara Cruz-Melguizo (Spain)
10:25 - 10:45	Cervix <25 mm: IPD meta-analysis of vaginal progesterone in singletons & twins	Roberto Romero (USA)
10:45 - 11:00	Discussion	
11:00 - 11:30 Coffee break		
11:30 - 16:20	Congenital heart defects Discussants: Vita Zidere (UK), Marietta Charakida (UK)	
11:30 - 11:50	Tetralogy of Fallot	Vita Zidere (UK)
11:50 - 12:10	Coarctation of the aorta	Marietta Charakida (UK)
12:10 - 12:40	CHD: discussion of cases	Zidere, Charakida, Chaoui
12:40 - 12:50	Fetal venous system	Simcha Yagel (Israel)
12:50 - 13:00	Anomalies of aortic arch - fetal US and postnatal MRI / CT	Reuven Achiron (Israel)
13:00 - 14:30 Lunch break		
14:30 - 14:37	CHD: absent pulmonary valve syndrome	Roland Axt-Fliedner (Germany)
14:37 - 14:44	CHD: pulmonary atresia - prediction of outcome	Jesus Rodriguez Calvo (Spain)
14:44 - 14:51	CHD: X and V signs in 1st trimester screening	Anitha Shettikeri (India)
14:51 - 14:58	CHD: cardiac axis and V sign angle in 1st trimester screening	Mingming Zheng (China)
14:58 - 15:05	CHD: 1st trimester screening by simplified examination	Carmela Votino (Italy)
15:05 - 15:12	CHD: incidence in IVF / ICSI pregnancy	Paolo Cavoretto (Italy)
15:12 - 15:22	CHD: head growth and Doppler	Roland Axt-Fliedner (Germany)
15:22 - 15:29	CHD: fetal growth and placental perfusion	Paolo Cavoretto (Italy)
15:29 - 15:36	CHD: placental epigenetic biomarkers of isolated VSD	Ray Bahado-Singh (USA)
15:36 - 15:43	CHD: submicroscopic chromosomal aberrations	Zhu Zhang (China)
15:43 - 16:00	CHD: technical aspects of fetal cardiac interventions	Marzena Debska (Poland)
16:00 - 16:07	Fetoscopic transesophageal atrial pacing in tachyarrhythmia	Julien Stirnemann (France)
16:07 - 16:20	CHD: discussion	
16:20 - 16:30	Fetal bowel dilation	Reuven Achiron (Israel)
16:30 - 17:30 Coffee break		
17:30 - 19:00	First trimester scan Discussants: Katia Bilardo (Netherlands), Rabih Chaoui (Germany)	
17:30 - 17:37	11-13 w scan: hypoplasia / aplasia of the vermis	Reinhard Altmann (Austria)
17:37 - 17:44	11-13 w scan: maxillary gap and facial cleft	Robert Lachmann (Germany)
17:44 - 18:05	11-13 w scan: discussion of cases	Oliver Kagan (Germany)
18:05 - 18:20	Role of ultrasound in the era of cfDNA testing: 1st trimester ultrasound diagnosis of fetal defects	Katia Bilardo (Netherlands)
18:20 - 19:00		Rabih Chaoui (Germany)

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Wednesday 28th June 2017

18:00 – 18:30

Prediction and prevention of preeclampsia

Discussants: John Hyett (Australia), Ahmet Baschat (USA)
Gerry Visser (Netherlands), Kypros Nicolaides (UK)

10:00 – 10:07

1st trimester: prediction of PE by the combined test

Neil O'Gorman (France)

10:07 – 10:14

1st trimester: prediction of PE by the combined test

Jiri Sonek (USA)

10:14 – 10:21

1st trimester: prediction of PE/FGRI/UD by the combined test

Emmanuel Bujold (Canada)

10:21 – 10:28

1st trimester: prediction of PE/FGRI/UD by serum AFP

Ebru Celik (Turkey)

10:28 – 10:35

1st trimester: quality assessment of uterine artery Doppler

Daniel Rotnik (Australia)

10:35 – 10:42

1st trimester: new technique for uterine artery Doppler

Olivier Drouin (Canada) /

Liona Poon (HK)

Zsobia Benko (UK)

10:42 – 10:52

1st trimester: prediction of PE in twins

10:52 – 11:00

Discussion

11:00 – 11:30

Coffee break

11:30 – 11:40

Prediction of PE by proteomics and metabolomics

Ray Bahado-Singh (USA)

11:40 – 11:47

Prediction of PE by serum GDF15 and HtrA3

Fabricio Costa (Australia)

11:47 – 11:54

2nd trimester: prediction of PE by NICE, ACOG, FMF

Fabricio Costa (Australia)

11:54 – 12:01

2nd trimester: stratification of care based on prediction of PE

Magdalena Litwinska (UK)

12:01 – 12:11

3rd trimester: prediction and diagnosis of PE by sFLT-1 / PLGF

Stefan Verlohren (Germany)

12:11 – 12:18

3rd trimester: prediction of PE by serum MR-proANP

Cahit Birdir (Germany)

12:18 – 12:30

Pregnancy hypertension: maternal cardiac function

Basky Thilaganathan (UK)

12:30 – 12:38

Pregnancy hypertension: angiogenic and cardiovascular markers

Stefan Verlohren (Germany)

12:38 – 12:45

Diagnosis of PE: value of urine PCR

Eran Ashwal (Israel)

12:45 – 12:52

Diagnosis of PE: effect of race on urine PCR

Nikos Kametas (UK)

12:52 – 13:00

Diagnosis of PE: need for validated blood pressure monitor

Diane Nzelu (UK)

13:00 – 14:30

Lunch break

14:30 – 14:37

Implications of previous gestational hypertension

Dan Biris (UK)

14:37 – 14:44

Implications of maternal obesity

Argyro Syngelaki (UK)

14:44 – 14:51

Implications of chronic hypertension

Anca Panaitescu (UK)

14:51 – 15:00

Discussion

15:00 – 15:15

ASPREE trial: prevention of preterm PE

Liona Poon (UK)

15:15 – 15:25

ASPREE trial: effect on term PE

David Wright (UK)

15:25 – 15:40

ASPREE trial: implications

Kypros Nicolaides (UK)

15:40 – 15:50

Prevention of PE: going beyond aspirin

Ahmet Baschat (USA)

15:50 – 16:00

Prevention of PE: omeprazole

John Hyett (Australia)

16:00 – 16:10

The Hawthorne effect

Gerry Visser (Netherlands)

16:10 – 16:30

Discussion

16:30 – 16:45

Early screening tests – effect on healthcare costs

Carl Weiner (USA)

16:45 – 17:00

Intrapartum mortality and severe asphyxia

Zarko Alfrevic (UK)

Fetal and neonatal medicine from basic research to clinical practice

Fetal Diagnosis and Therapy
Editor: E. Gratacos, Barcelona

Fetal Diagnosis and Therapy
2016, 1072 pages
Hardcover, 100 illustrations
978-3-318-28121-0
CHF 120.00, EUR 85.00

Intrapartum Mortality and Severe Asphyxia
Editors: H.L. Halliday, Newcastle
C.P. Spear, Newcastle

Intrapartum Mortality and Severe Asphyxia
2016, 107 pages
Hardcover, 10 illustrations
978-3-318-28121-0
CHF 45.00, EUR 32.00

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Thursday 29th June 2017

09:00 - 11:00

Maternal fetal disease

Discussants: Yves Ville (France), Gerry Visser (Netherlands)

09:00 - 09:07

CMV infection: role of HIG therapy

09:07 - 09:14

CMV infection: role of antiretrovirals

09:14 - 09:21

CMV infection: role of MRI

09:21 - 09:28

Zika virus: exposure and consequences

09:28 - 09:35

Zika virus: ultrasound abnormalities in affected fetuses

09:35 - 09:42

Appendicitis: role of emergency MRI

09:42 - 09:49

Bariatric surgery: effect on insulin resistance

09:49 - 09:56

GDM: late preterm birth and neonatal morbidity

09:56 - 10:10

Updates on diabetes mellitus and pregnancy

10:10 - 10:30

Maternal autoantibodies and fetal defects

10:30 - 11:00

Cases of maternal-fetal medicine

Oliver Kagan (Germany)

Yves Ville (France)

Shlomo Lipitz (Israel)

Carlota Rodo (Spain)

Carol Gisela Rueda (Colombia)

Eldad Katorza (Israel)

Tanya Maric (UK)

Katja Bricej (Slovenia)

Gerry Visser (Netherlands)

Anca Panaitescu (UK)

Surabhi Nanda (UK)

11:00 - 11:30

Coffee break

11:30 - 13:00

Labor and delivery

Discussants: Gerry Visser (Netherlands), Yves Ville (France)

11:30 - 11:37

Prediction of adverse outcome at 20 weeks

11:37 - 11:47

Prediction of SGA with adverse outcome

11:47 - 12:00

Cerebro-placental ratio: prediction of fetal distress in labor

12:00 - 12:15

Fetal head size and labor outcome

12:15 - 12:30

Re-engineering the interpretation of fetal monitoring

12:30 - 12:37

Sonographic assessment of progression angle

12:37 - 12:44

Sonographic prediction of successful induction of labor

12:44 - 12:51

Intrapartum sonographic monitoring of progress of labor

12:51 - 13:00

Discussion

George Papaioannou (Greece)

Asma Khalil (UK)

Ranjit Akolekar (UK)

Simcha Yagel (Israel)

Mark Evans (USA)

Francesco Conversano (Italy)

Magdalena Fiolna (UK)

Alex Frick (UK)

13:00 - 14:30

Lunch break

A case of early recurrent pregnancy loss caused by paternal translocation t(3;8) (q13;q24)

Kavecán I, Privrodski B, Obrenović M, Redzek Mudrinic T

Medical Faculty, University of Novi Sad, Institute for Children and Youth Health Care of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Objective

To present the implications in early pregnancies of a familial balanced translocation 3;8. Balanced Translocations are structural chromosomal rearrangements that rarely cause problems in carriers, but could cause pregnancy complications. When balanced carriers transmit the rearrangement, it can result in a significant chromosomal imbalance in the offspring.

Methods

This is a case report.

Results

A 25 year-old woman and 29 year-old man were referred to our geneticist because of recurrent pregnancy loss (5 times) at 6-10 weeks of gestation. They have one healthy female child from the first pregnancy. Karyotypes of couple were performed, and the karyotype of man was 46,XY, t(3;8)(q13;q24). The woman had normal karyotype. After 5 miscarriages she had a normal pregnancy with the same balanced translocation as the father has. Recurrent miscarriages could be caused by unbalanced chromosomal aberrations due to balanced parent's chromosomal rearrangement. In this case a paternal balanced translocation 3;8 was detected.

Conclusion

Recurrent miscarriages could be traumatic for couple. For these cases there is no treatment before conceiving. Preimplantation genetic diagnosis is one possibility in some cases and genetic information is necessary.